

The influence of local affiliation on co-variation:

Evidence from Aroostook County English

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Abstract: This paper investigates whether local affiliation, which has been shown to be a strong predictor for individual linguistic variables, also promotes systematic variation between usage rates. Drawing on a corpus of sociolinguistic interviews from a small, understudied variety of English spoken at the US-Canadian border in Northern Maine as well as an innovative, discourse-based approach to measuring place identity, the analytical focus is on three morphosyntactic variables with similar sociolinguistic profiles and social meanings (*was* leveling, demonstrative *them*, and preterite *come*). Results show that speakers with high local affiliation, especially men who embody the locally relevant persona of the hard-working *County Boy*, tend to have similar repertoires. However, usage varies widely and are only significantly correlated for the two agreement features (i.e., nonstandard *was* and *them*). These findings suggest that speakers with high local affiliation do not share a static lect, but combine features that index localness in dynamic ways.

Keywords: place identity, co-occurrence, co-variation, Northern Maine, morphosyntactic variation

1. Introduction

The study of place identity has a long history in Variationist Sociolinguistics, starting with Labov's (1963) landmark study on the social motivations behind two ongoing sound changes in Martha's Vineyard. Over the years, the phenomenon has surfaced under different names, including "local loyalty" (Ito & Preston 1998), "rootedness" (Reed 2018, 2020) and "local affiliation" (Roberts 2016), and has been operationalized in different ways, depending on the local context and the research questions under investigation (see Carmichael & Reed 2025:20-22 for an overview). Regardless of how researchers refer to the phenomenon or how they define it, they often find that it is a strong predictor for linguistic variation. As is common in Variationist Sociolinguistics, most of these studies consider one or more variables in isolation (see Guy 2013:64). However, hardly any studies examine whether speakers with high local affiliation combine linguistic variables in systematic ways (or, in other words, display co-variation), as we might expect if they had some sort of shared sociolect (Guy 2013).¹ To address this gap in the literature, this study will investigate speech production data from four small, rural communities in Aroostook County, Maine (USA), whose inhabitants traditionally define themselves and their lifestyle in opposition to the politically and economically dominant southern part of the state (namely, Dyer Brook, Merrill, Oakfield, and Smyrna). Specifically, it will investigate whether individuals who closely align themselves with local values share the same inventory of forms that have come to index localness (i.e., whether these features "co-occur") and whether there is a systematic relationship between their rates of usage for these features (i.e., whether these features "co-vary", see Guy & Hinskens 2016:3).

The linguistic variables that were chosen for this study are three morphosyntactic alternations whose nonstandard variants have locally become associated with qualities such as being 'hard-working' and 'self-sufficient'.² These are *was* leveling in non-existential constructions

(i.e., the variation between *was* and *were* with first person plural, second person singular, plural, and generic, and third person plural subjects, as in 1)^{3,4}, demonstrative *them* (i.e., the variation between the demonstrative determiners *them*, *these*, and *those*, as in 2), and preterite *come* (i.e., the variation between the preterite forms *come* and *came*, as in 3).

1. We **was** really close. (Carrie Beers, female-presenting, born 1992)⁵
2. It's one of **them** jobs, you know. (Raymond Radcliffe, male-presenting, born 1956)
3. But he **come** home every weekend. (Alexandra Miller, female-presenting, born 1950)

All three alternations are attested throughout the English-speaking world, from the UK to North America and beyond (see Schneider 2004 for a synopsis, and AUTHOR 2022 for a more recent overview of studies), meaning they are not regionally distinctive. Previous work indicates that the use of their non-standard variants is frequently correlated with social characteristics of a speaker such as age (*was*: Tagliamonte 1998; *them*: Hazen, Hamilton & Vacovsky 2011; *come*: Jankowski & Tagliamonte 2022; *inter alia*), gender (*was*: Hay & Schreyer 2004; *them*: Hazen, Hamilton & Vacovsky 2011; *come*: Tagliamonte 2001; *inter alia*), and education (*was*: Hazen 2014; *them*: Hazen, Hamilton & Vacovsky; *come*: Tagliamonte 2001; *inter alia*), with increased use among older speakers, men, and speakers with little or no post-secondary education. Why would these morphosyntactic features, which are by no means unique to Aroostook County, come to index qualities that are considered typical for the area, such as being ‘hard-working’ and ‘self-sufficient’? The answer lies in the community’s history.

Aroostook County, or “The County,” as the locals affectionately call it, is both the largest and most sparsely populated county in the state of Maine (see Figure 1). Once a relatively affluent

area, the County has experienced drastic economic decline due to less demand for its two main industries: lumber and potato farming. As a result, it has lost 20% of its population since 1970, with many younger folks opting to move down south for better educational and professional opportunities (Plimpton Research 2016).

Figure 1. Map of New England and New Brunswick with Aroostook County highlighted. CT = Connecticut, USA; MA = Massachusetts, USA; ME = Maine, USA; NB = New Brunswick, Canada; NH = New Hampshire, USA; RI = Rhode Island, USA; VT = Vermont, USA.⁶

Despite these challenges, individuals from the County tend to be very proud of their roots and often highlight the hard work and determination it took to live the area. This is also reflected in historical accounts of the region, such as the following description from railroad historian Stewart Holbrook:

Aroostook is a county of Maine. It is more than a county. It is a region, an empire, a state of mind, for Aroostook, as it is known in Maine, was the last frontier in eastern United States and the material and spiritual effects are still to be seen there and felt. There are two reasons why Aroostook, alone in New England, remained frontier country up to little more than fifty years ago. For one thing it was the most remote section of New England. For the other, its sovereignty was in doubt until 1842, when the Webster Ashburn Treaty was signed by the United States and Britain. (Holbrook 1947, cited in Angier 1985:85)⁷

Similar discourses circulate to this day. In its promotional materials, the town of Merrill, where part of the fieldwork for this project took place, praises its founder, Captain William Merrill, for managing to build a homestead in the early nineteenth century is still standing despite the harsh conditions in the area, attributing the same kind of resilience and to Merrill's current-day residents:

The town of Merrill is still populated with people who possess the same work ethic, spirit of adventure and Yankee ingenuity as Capt. Merrill. In the early days of Merrill, farming was necessary for survival; the early settlers had to provide or make do for their own needs. The "Can Do" spirit is very much alive in Merrill residents to this day. (Town of Merrill 2019)

Remarkably similar sentiments can be found in the County Corpus, where several speakers pride themselves on being self-sufficient and independent because they had to be for such a long time (4-5):

4. I think the County people hold themselves to a higher ethic. [...] If you was brought up in the woods or on a farm you had to do everything yourself, your mechanic work, any type of work. And you got so that you could do it all - or thought you could. (Liam Gordon, male-presenting, born 1950)
5. If you were from Aroostook County you had good worth -- work ethics, that's why they hired you. And hard work doesn't -- doesn't scare you. (James Clarke, male-presenting, born 1952)

In many descriptions of local life, participants directly or indirectly contrast this idea of self-sufficiency and manual labor with life in the more densely populated southern part of the state (6-7). This is in line with Bucholtz & Hall's (2004) observation that individuals often discursively create and maintain their identities by positioning themselves in opposition to others (see Remlinger 2017; Bigelow 2019, and Schlegl 2019 for additional examples from the literature on language and place):

6. AM: We're the other Maine.

Author: The other Maine?

AM: Yes. Most people don't know there's anything above Bangor. You know, south -- Down the southern end of the state they don't realize that there's people up here. So when you tell 'em you're from Northern Maine, "Oh, you mean Bangor?" It's like, "Uh no, an hour and a half above that."

(Alexandra Miller, female-presenting, age 67)

7. They wanna make us a park up here now, you know. Uh, but you always—for years, they've always referred to us as Northern Maine and Southern Maine. Two Maines. [...] I think they just don't realize that-- You know, until they come up and see that there's nothing up here. You know, that, uh, they don't take it into consideration that you know, we're not like them down there that's got big-- You know, bigger population, more jobs, more things to do, you know. Up here we watch the snow come in the fall and watch it melt in the spring. (Raymond Radcliffe, male-presenting, age 62)

Southern Maine is seen as the political and economic center of the state, and its fast-paced lifestyle with plenty of white-collar jobs and activities is constructed as being diametrically opposed to the northern way of life, which is characterized by hard manual labor and outdoorsy activities.

Informal observation during fieldwork for this project showed that linguistically, this distance is often expressed by adopting non-standard morphological features, such as *was*, *them*, and, to a lesser extent, *come* (which is more wide-spread in the community than the other two features), especially by middle-aged and older men who work in the lumber industry or other physically demanding fields who see themselves in opposition to the south with its more white-collar work force (erasing the strong tradition of fishing and other blue-collar professions in the

south). Locally, these men from the north are often referred to as *County Boys*, a character type that unites many of the traditional, masculine-coded values that been associated with the local settler population since the days of Captain Merrill: physical strength, grit, and a strong affinity for the outdoors.⁸ Several of the participants in this study specifically mention this persona during fieldwork (8-9):

8. Guy from Aroostook County. [laughs] Redneck stuff. [laughs] Trapping. Yeah, hunting, fishing, trapping, Snow sleds in the wintertime, ATVs in the summertime, four-wheelers, yeah. Bad boys, bad boys. (James Clark, male-presenting, age 66)
9. Like, a County Boy you'll quickly know. Like, even in Portland. They're gonna have probably a T-shirt that's either tucked in or, like [laughs], somewhat shorter. They're gonna have their belt on and they're even in work boots or, like, hiking-type sneakers. And there's gonna be camo somewhere on them. [laughs] (Hannah Leslie, female-presenting, born 1979)

At first blush, the fact that these speakers recruit morphosyntactic variables to index their alignment with local values may seem surprising, especially considering that researchers have long assumed that morphosyntactic features are less likely to be recruited for expressing aspects of a speaker's identity since they tend to have "quite fixed social meanings associated with external facts like class and particularly education" (Eckert 2018:190). However, it may actually be these class- and education-based connotations that make these features so suitable for indexing alignment with the northern way of life because they clearly set speakers apart from the south of the state, with its government buildings, white-collar jobs, and educational institutions. Similar

links between morphosyntactic variation and traditionally masculine-coded values such as hard labor and a strong connection to nature have been observed in Schlegl's (2019) study of language and identity in Northern Ontario, prompting her to suggest that there may be a pre-existing link between grammatical nonstandardness and disregard for (linguistic) prescriptivism, which speakers recruit to index their disalignment with people and institutions that embrace an urban lifestyle, which (to them) includes speaking standard English (see Schlegl 2019). Participant observation suggests that the same may be true for a subset of the population in Aroostook County, especially those who embrace the characteristics often associated with *County Boys*: hard-working, fiercely independent, with a penchant for outdoor activities.

This study will explore whether those who most strongly embrace traditional local values (many of which are attributed to County Boys) indeed use the nonstandard variants *was*, *them*, and *come*, and whether they systematically vary their rates of usage. To accomplish this task, it will draw on an innovative, discourse-based approach to quantifying local affiliation that was specifically developed to capture locally relevant distinctions. The paper is organized as follows: The next section will lay out the theoretical background of this work, including situating it in sociolinguistic literature on place identity and co-variation. Next, the data and methods will be outlined, with a particular focus on the ethnographically informed metric for operationalizing local affiliation that was developed for this study. Then, the results of the study will be presented and embedded in the research literature. In the end, a conclusion will sum up the main points of the analysis and discuss the study's implications for future work.

2. Background

Place identity

Orientation to place has been invoked to explain patterns of variation starting from the earliest studies in Variationist Sociolinguistics. In his ground-breaking study of Martha's Vineyard, for example, Labov (1963) showed that participation in a locally relevant sound change – the centralization of the nuclei in the diphthongs /ay/ and /aw/ - was most advanced among young men working in the fishing industry who sought to distinguish themselves from the mainlanders who flocked to the island during the summer and were buying up a local real estate, thus turning the local economy on its head. Ever since, researchers have investigated place-based variation in a variety of communities, drawing on both qualitative and quantitative approaches (see Montgomery & Moore 2017 and Cornips & Rooij 2018 for two excellent examples of both). Many studies focus on rural areas: Hazen (2002), for instance, investigates the influence of what he calls “cultural identity” on the past and present realizations of the verb *to be* in Warren County, a small, Southern community in North Carolina, showing that that speakers who strongly align themselves with the local lifestyle (especially in terms of educational and career aspirations) have much higher rates of nonstandard *was* than those who have a more supralocal orientation. Reed (2018, 2020) analyzes the use of /ay/-monophthongization and rising pitch accents in East Tennessee and East North Carolina, showing that both features are used to reflect speakers' orientation towards Southern Appalachia, especially in relation to the broader US South. Schlegl (2019) and Hawkey (2019) examine vastly different geographical locations (northern Ontario and southern France), but share a common focus on morphosyntactic features, which have received comparatively little attention in the literature on language and place (but see Childs & van Herk 2018 and Beaman 2021). Using a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches, both studies find correlations between alignment with local values and customs and some (but not all) of the features they look at. Both find that rates of usage do not necessarily reveal how or why speakers are using particular forms

(especially since some nonstandard morphosyntactic variants are incredibly rare), highlighting the importance of looking at qualitative differences for explaining patterns of variation. Within New England, Roberts (2016) shows that local affiliation, in combination with ethnographic observations about individual life choices and the history of the community, can explain interspeaker differences among her sample of Vermont speakers that would otherwise be difficult to interpret.

Despite the high number of studies on rural communities, the study of language and place is by no means confined to remote locales. Many of these show that place identity is intricately linked to social factors such as gender (Monka, Quist & Skovse 2020), race (Podesva 2016; King, 2021), and class (Ilbury 2022), as well as their intersections (Calder & King 2022). Take, for example, Monka, Quist & Skovse's (2020) study, which examines the relationship between place attachment and non-standard variants among teenagers in two very different communities in Denmark, one a multi-ethnic suburban housing district, the other a mono-ethnic village. The authors find that participants with the highest attachment in both communities indeed used more nonstandard variants, but that this correlation was stronger for boys than for girls. Similar findings have emerged in Monka's (2013) earlier work as well as Beaman (2021), suggesting that male-presenting speakers may be more likely to express their local affiliation by linguistic means than female-presenting ones, which jibes with informal observations during fieldwork for this project.⁹

Recent work has shown that place identity is not just influenced by social group membership, but also individuals' attitudes, goals and aspirations. Mobility seems to play a particularly important role in this context, with speakers who are actively planning on leaving a place often embracing supralocal features more so than their peers (Hazen 2002; Knee & van Herk 2013; King 2021). Research on geographically mobile individuals has shown that these individuals do not

necessarily leave their ‘old’ linguistic repertoire behind; in fact, they often actively use it to (dis)align with their new place of residence (Beaman 2021), regardless of whether they moved by choice (Nycz 2018) or not (Carmichael 2017, 2023). As such, they show that an individual’s relationship to place is not fixed; instead, it can vary over time and depending on the situation.

Coherence, co-occurrence, and co-variation

As mentioned above, one thing that most studies mentioned above have in common – like most studies in the field of Variationist Sociolinguistics (Guy 2013:64) – is that they tend to focus on individual features. If they do focus on more than one feature, they do not consider how the presence of one feature relates to that of another. One notable exception is Beaman’s (2021) longitudinal study of six phonological and six morphosyntactic features in Swabia. In contrast to this study, Beaman’s work is more concerned with overall dialect density rather than the relationship between individual variables with similar social meanings.

When considering variables with similar social meanings, as in our case, we may expect that those speakers who have one of the features may also be more likely to have the others and use them at similar rates or, as Guy (2013) would call it, be linguistically “coherent”. In other words, a coherent speaker is one who uses the same features as other individuals in their social group (e.g., a particular social class or ethnic group). If there is more than one feature associated with this group, the speaker’s rates of usage for these features would be expected to be positively correlated with each other. In sum, if a speaker has high rates of one feature associated with this social group, they would also be expected to have high rates of other features associated with said group.

Guy (2013:64) cautions that finding systematic co-variation between linguistic variables in individual speakers' output is far from a foregone conclusion. Specifically, he points to insights provided by studies in the tradition of the third wave of sociolinguistics, which show that speakers are not automata that simply reflect membership in different social groups (Eckert 2012). They have agency and combine different linguistic features to create identities, align or disalign themselves with their interlocutor, or convey other types of social meaning, a process Eckert (2008) refers to as "bricolage". This is nicely illustrated in Podesva's (2006) case study of Reagan, a young professional he recorded in different situations. When talking to his friends, Reagan combines numerous linguistic variants associated with expressiveness (such as high rates of consonant cluster reduction, falling intonation contours with high f0 levels, as well as frequent use of falsetto with comparatively long duration). Reagan's use of all these features, in combination with him talking about enjoying dancing and drinking, give rise to what Podesva calls a "partier style" (Podesva 2006:184) that stands in opposition to Reagan's more restrained self-presentation when talking to his supervisor at work. Combining features in this way allows Reagan to portray himself in a specific way in interaction. Reagan's use of these variables varies substantially across recording situations, leading Podesva to conclude that "styles characterize certain speakers in certain situations, perhaps with certain addressees" (Podesva 2006:185). This casts doubt on the idea that speakers are linguistically coherent all the time. However, if there is any systematic co-variation between features associated with high local affiliation, it would likely be in informal conversations about the area, such as the ones analyzed in this study.

Previous work on socially motivated co-variation has yielded inconclusive results. Examining four variables in a large corpus of sociolinguistic interviews with 20 native speakers of Brazilian Portuguese, Guy (2013) finds significant correlations for four out of six possible variable

pairs. However, three of these can be explained by linguistic motivations, whereby the realization of one variable influences that of another (such as the deletion of word-final /s/ automatically resulting in the non-realization of plural marker /s/). He further finds stronger correlations among women than men. While the gender differences can potentially be accounted for by appealing to different demands on these speakers' language use in the professional sphere, they cast doubt on the idea that there is a systematic relationship between social categories and coherence. Analyzing four variables in Nain English, a variety spoken by an Indigenous community in Nunatsiavut, Thorburn (2014) does find some evidence for socially-motivated coherence, with younger women who learned English as their first language patterning more similarly to each other than the rest of community. Given that English was introduced fairly recently in the community, the lack of coherence among other groups is not surprising, though. More recently, studies have moved away from broad, macro-social categories to other characteristics that might unite individuals. For example, Waters & Tagliamonte (2017) explore whether there are any characteristics that unite leaders of linguistic change. While they do unveil some significant correlations between ongoing changes in Toronto, most variable pairs show no statistically significant relationships. Nagy & Gadanidis (2022) report similar findings for ongoing changes in heritage Italian in Toronto, leaving the exact relationship between membership in particular social groups and co-variation unclear.

While the evidence for socially motivated coherence is spotty, there is reason to believe that structural similarities promote co-variation. One piece of evidence comes from Guy (2013), discussed above, who finds that the majority of significant correlations between variables can be traced to one feature determining the realization of the other. Additional evidence comes from Oushiro & Guy (2015), Oushiro (2016), and Esposito (2023), all of whom find significant

correlations between structurally related features in their work (such as agreement-related features or vowel classes that are undergoing fronting in parallel). Taken together, these findings suggest that features with structural similarities are more likely to co-vary.

Recently, researchers have shown an increasing level of interest in the role socially recognized figures, so-called *personae*, play in the way individuals combine linguistic variables. For example, examining FACE and GOAT ungliding in two Ontario communities, Bigelow (2019) finds that those with the most advanced ungliding tend to have the most rural orientation. She argues that this trend is mediated by the so-called *Neo-Hoser*, a young working-class man from small town Canada with interest outdoorsy activities such as hunting and fishing. Looking at variation in the multilingual and multiethnic island country of Singapore, Starr (2021) finds that younger speakers increasingly combine local, Singapore English vowel realizations with postvocalic rhoticity, a feature often associated with American English, to index a new, (foreign-) educated identity. Focusing on several ongoing changes in Sacramento, California, Esposito (2023) similarly finds that younger speakers increasingly combine features in line with an emerging character type of a young urbanite. All three studies show that the combination of features is highly dependent on their social meaning within the local semiotic landscape, highlighting that an in-depth understanding of the community is crucial for making sense of the observed patterns of variation.

Hypotheses

Based on the review of the existing literature, as well as the author's observations during fieldwork, the following hypotheses are put forth:

- 1) First, given the similar social profiles and indexical meanings of *was* leveling, demonstrative *them*, and preterite *come*, it is expected that the nonstandard variants *was*, *them*, and *come* are favored by speakers with high local affiliation.
- 2) Second, given that some speakers may not be variable, it is expected that the number of nonstandard variants in speakers' repertoire is positively correlated with local affiliation.
- 3) It is expected that usage rates are correlated for speakers with high local affiliation, meaning individuals with high rates of *was* would also have high rates of *them* and *come*.
- 4) Finally, correlations for features with structural similarities (such as the two agreement features, *was* leveling and demonstrative *them*) will be stronger than for other feature combinations.

3. Data and methods

Data

The data for this project come from ethnographic interviews with native speakers of English who were born and raised in Aroostook County, Maine. Specifically, participants come from four neighboring communities in the southern part of Aroostook County, Maine (see Figure 1): Dyer Brook (population = 306), Merrill (population = 195), Oakfield (population = 763), and Smyrna (population = 506, U.S. Census Bureau 2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2018e).¹⁰ All interviews were conducted by the author during the summer of 2018, with speakers being recorded alone or in dyads. For the present analysis, a subsample of 30 speakers was analyzed, stratified by age and gender (see Table 1). The sample consists of 28 European Americans and two Native Americans, which mirrors the ethnic make-up of the communities. Twenty-nine speakers are cis and one is a

trans woman. For the analysis, her data was grouped with the other female-presenting speakers. Since the interviews were collected with the purpose of investigating the relationship between language and place, all participants were asked about various aspects of their lives that have been associated with place identity in the past, such as their family history, their preferred pastimes, and their involvement in local social structures (see Roberts 2016).

The interview data is supplemented with information from participant observation, including time spent socializing with community members as well as visits to local museums and events over a two-month period. Thanks to family connections in the area, I was able to enter the community as the ‘friend of a friend’ (Milroy 1980), allowing me access to a wide variety of social networks among the local population. Unfortunately, this did not include the local Amish population, which has resided in the area since 1996 (Town of Smyrna 2020). While the participants in my study described the overall relationship between the local settler population and the Amish as good, there is limited interaction between the two groups. Given the limited scope of this paper, future work will have to explore these ties as well as their linguistic implications in more detail.

Table 1: Speaker sample

Age group	Gender		TOTAL
	Male-presenting	Female-presenting	
18-29	5	5	10
30-59	5	5	10
60+	5	5	10
TOTAL	15	15	30

Procedure

Relevant tokens were extracted using AntConc (Anthony 2019). This includes (1) all non-existential constructions where both *was* and *were* can occur (in Aroostook County English, this includes all non-existential constructions with first person plural, second person (singular, plural, and generic), third person plural, and plural NP subjects); (2) all instances of demonstrative determiners *them*, *those*, and *these*;¹¹ and (3) all instances of the verb *come* in the past tense. This approach yielded 624 tokens of *was* leveling, 239 tokens of demonstrative *them*, and 211 tokens of preterite *come*. All tokens were coded a variety of social and linguistic factors that are likely to influence all three features (such as the individual speaker, their local affiliation, age, gender, and level of education) as well as several feature-specific linguistic predictors. Then, each feature was analyzed using distributional analysis and conditional inference trees (Tagliamonte & Baayen 2012) in R (R Core Team 2021). To determine if there were any correlations between the use of individual features, Pearson's product moment correlations between usage rates were calculated. Finally, to investigate whether speakers with a high level of local affiliation were more likely to use nonstandard variants, a fixed effects logistic regression was run on the number of nonstandard variants speakers used in their interviews.

Operationalizing local affiliation in Southern Aroostook County

Previous work used a variety of ways to operationalize local affiliation, ranging from detailed surveys about values and pastime activities (Reed 2018, 2020) to classifications based on ethnographic observations and interview content (e.g., Bigelow 2019; Monka, Quist & Skovse 2020; Roberts 2016; Schlegl 2019; Sneller 2019). One thing that all these approaches have in common is that they conceptualize local affiliation as multifaceted - an amalgamation of individuals' personal histories and/or their characteristics and behaviors. This approach posits that

none of these components alone can predict an individual's relation to place; after all, someone whose family has a long history in the area may be more likely to be highly involved in the community. However, they may also decide that local life is not for them and build a new life elsewhere. Carmichael (2023) argues that these complex entanglements can successfully be captured by designing ethnographically informed metrics that condense all locally relevant components into a single score, which can then be used in quantitative analyses. She refers to these measures as *multidimensional place orientation metrics*, or short MPOMs. This section introduces the metric that was developed to explore the relationship between local affiliation and the co-variation between *was* leveling, demonstrative *them*, and preterite *come* in Southern Aroostook County.

Since this study was part of a larger project on language and place (AUTHOR 2022), including regional variation, all individuals who were interviewed were born and raised in Aroostook County or had moved there before their seventh birthday. Given that this excluded long-term residents and geographically mobile speakers, the metric exclusively focuses on speakers' orientation to place (rather than their family history), here defined as their alignment with ideas of what the area and the people living there are like (following Sneller 2019). Sneller (2019) illustrates this kind of approach using data from Philadelphia, PA. Drawing on historical data and media discourse about Philadelphia, she identifies two ideologies: that modern-day Philadelphians (similar to the Quakers who founded the city) are deeply suspicious of authority and that Philadelphia (and with it, its local variety of English) is an 'underdog,' constantly in the shadow of larger and more prestigious cities like New York City and Washington, DC. With these ideologies in mind, she coded her sociolinguistic interview data for how speakers' position themselves with regards to topics that are frequently governed by some form of authority (such as

swearing, drugs, sex, or getting in trouble) as well as how they feel about the fact that the local variety of English tends to be highly stigmatized, finding that speakers' orientation to these ideologies is a strong predictor for participation in this local sound change.

To identify locally relevant ideas of what it means to be from Southern Aroostook County, thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes in the data (Braun & Clarke 2006). Specifically, all mentions of what it means to be from the area were manually extracted and assigned initial codes. These themes were regularly revised to reflect relevant insights (Braun & Clarke 2006: 87). In the end, they were summarized into four main ideologies: people from the area

- (1) are hard-working and self-sufficient,
- (2) enjoy rural life and outdoor activities, especially hunting and fishing,
- (3) are down to earth and do not care what others think, and
- (4) are friendly and help each other in times of need.

Quantification

When developing the metric for this study, the biggest challenge was to synthesize these ideologies as well as relevant ethnographic observations into one score so they could be used as a predictor in statistical analyses. Sneller (2019) used a Likert scale to operationalize speakers' alignment with the two ideologies she had identified. However, this approach made it difficult to decide where exactly on the five-point Likert scale a speaker should fall, which poses a problem for replicability. To avoid this issue, the metric developed for this study takes a different approach: Building on Roberts (2016), the four ideologies mentioned above were translated into yes or no questions that

were used to code participants' interviews. Each positive answer was assigned one point, while each negative answer was assigned no points. These initial questions were supplemented by several additional questions based on the author's observations (including the fact that staying in Northern Maine was often a deliberate choice and that some participants avoided discussing potentially negative aspects of local life such as poverty, unemployment, and the effects of the opioid crisis). Once the questions were finalized, the author went through the interview transcripts and looked for the relevant information. In the end, each participant was assigned an individual local affiliation score based on the information they provided in the interview. The complete metric developed for this study can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: The multidimensional place orientation metric developed for this study

No.	Question	Yes	No
1	Does the interviewee describe themselves as hard-working, self-sufficient?	+1	+0
2	Does the interviewee mention past or present engagement in hunting?	+1	+0
3	Does the interviewee mention past or present engagement in other outdoor activities like fishing, snowmobiling, or ATVing?	+1	+0
4	Does the interviewee describe themselves as down to earth, enjoying the simple things in life?	+1	+0
5	Does the interviewee mention any instances where they helped other people?	+1	+0
6	Does the interviewee focus on the positive aspects of local life and culture?	+1	+0
7	Did the interviewee spend a limited time living outside of Northern Maine?	+1	+0

Participants' scores range from 2 to 6. On average, male-presenting participants have slightly higher scores (mean=4.7) than female-presenting participants (mean=3.8).

Coding

On top of local affiliation and traditional social factors such as age, gender presentation, and education, the data was coded for a variety of feature-specific predictors. Due to space constraints,

these cannot be discussed in detail here. For more information, please see AUTHOR (2022), chapter 6.3. For an overview of the complete coding schema, see Table 3. Note that race/ethnicity was not included in the model because the overwhelming majority of participants identified as white, leading to very small token numbers for the non-white group.

Table 3: Coding schema

Dependent variables	Codes
<i>Was/were</i> variation	was were
Demonstrative <i>them</i>	them these those
Preterite <i>come</i>	come came
Independent variables coded for all three variables	Levels
Local affiliation	Continuous, ranging from 2 (low) to 6 (high)
Age	Continuous, ranging from 19 to 70
Age group	Younger (18-29 years old) Middle-aged (30-59 years old) Older (60+ years old)
Gender	Male-presenting Female-presenting
Education	Some post-secondary education No post-secondary education
Independent variables coded for <i>was</i> leveling only	Levels
Polarity	Positive Negative
Subject	First person plural (we) Second person (you) Third person plural (they) NP plural
Independent variables coded for demonstrative <i>them</i> only	Levels
Proximity	Proximal Distal
Animacy	Generic Animate Inanimate

Presence of quantifier	Present Absent
Syntactic environment	Subject Object Prepositional phrase
Independent variables coded for preterite <i>come</i> only	
Presence of particle	Present Absent
Subject	First-person singular Third-person singular Other
Temporal ordering	First Second Not ordered

4. Results

Distributional analysis of the three variables reveals that nonstandard *was* and *them* are minority variants: the former makes up only 10.9% of all tokens ($n=68/624$), while the latter makes up 14.6% ($n=35/239$, compared to *these* at $97/239=40.6\%$ and *those* at $107/239=44.8\%$). The old preterite form *come*, on the other hand, is much more common, accounting for 46.4% of the data ($n=98/211$).

There is substantial individual variation in the use of the nonstandard variants. Indeed, some speakers do not use the nonstandard variants at all (*was*: $18/30=60\%$, *them*: $19/30=63.3\%$, *come*: $9/30=30\%$). For *them* and *come*, there are several individuals who did not have any variable contexts in their interviews (*them*: Carrie Beers and Megan Lawrence; *come*: Jane Brooks, Jason Brewer, Rachel Nelson, and Megan Lawrence). The remaining individuals – most of whom were born after 1973 and thus younger than 45 at the time of the interview – are not variable.

Plotting the distribution of nonstandard variants by speakers' local affiliation scores shows that rates of *was*, *them*, and *come* are highest among speakers with high scores (see Figure 2), as predicted. In fact, demonstrative *them* is only used by speakers with local affiliation scores of 5

and 6. Separate plots showing the distribution of variants by age group, gender, and education (not shown here due to space constraints) confirm that the variables pattern similar to other communities described in the literature, with higher rates of nonstandard features among older speakers, male-presenting speakers, and those without postsecondary education.

Figure 2. Nonstandard variants by local affiliation score.

To understand how the different predictors operate when considered at the same time, the data was analyzed using conditional inference trees (Tagliamonte & Baayen 2012) in R (R Core Team 2021), a method that uses recursive partitioning to determine relationships between a

dependent variable (here, the three variables under investigation) and various predictors. For the analysis, which was conducted using the party package (Hothorn, Hornik & Zeileis 2006), all social factors (i.e., local affiliation, age, gender, and education) were taken into consideration as well as whatever linguistic factors were relevant for each variable. The results are seen in Figures 3-5.

Figure 3. Conditional inference tree for *was* leveling.

Figure 4. Conditional inference tree demonstrative *them*.

Figure 5. Conditional inference tree preterite *come*.

The conditional inference trees show that higher rates of nonstandard variants are indeed found among those with higher levels of local affiliation. However, local affiliation interacts with the

remaining factors in different ways. For example, for *was*, it is mostly male presenting speakers who use the nonstandard form (Figure 3, node 1), especially with first person plural and second person subjects (Figure 3, node 5) and when they have a local affiliation score of 5 or 6 (Figure 3, node 8). For *come*, rates are highest for middle-aged and older speakers (Figure 5, node 7), with some differences depending on whether a particle is present (Figure 5, node 8); local affiliation matters, but exclusively for female-presenting speakers with some education (Figure 5, node 5). For demonstrative *them*, the most important predictor is proximity (Figure 4, node 1), with speakers with high local affiliation having a completely different system compared to those who do not. More precisely, those with high local affiliation use both *them* and *those* in distal contexts (Figure 4, node 4), while those with low scores are barely variable (Figure 4, node 3). Hazen, Hamilton & Vacovsky (2011) also find two different distal systems in their sample. Unfortunately, they did not code for local affiliation, raising the question if this type of interaction may be more common in other (rural) communities. Either way, the results show that despite superficial similarities in distribution, the social and linguistic predictors for each feature interact in unique ways, suggesting it is unlikely that high local affiliation will promote similar usage rates.

The fact that only some speakers use the nonstandard variants *was*, *them*, and *come* raises the question whether there may be a correlation between local affiliation and how many nonstandard features speakers have in their repertoire. Figure 6 shows the number of nonstandard variants speakers had in their interview by their local affiliation score. The positive slope indicates that there is indeed a correlation. This is confirmed by a linear fixed effects regression, which shows that local affiliation is the only significant predictor for the number of features speakers use when all other social factors are being held constant (see Table 4).

Figure 6. Number of nonstandard features by local affiliation score.

This effect still approaches significance when the number of words each speaker uttered are included in the model (estimate=1.09, $SE=0.58$, $t=0.190$, $p=0.10$), highlighting that this is not a matter of some speakers contributing more data than others. Taken together, these findings confirm that speakers with high local affiliation indeed tend to have similar repertoires, or inventories, of variants.

Table 4: Fixed-effects linear regression on number of nonstandard variants by local affiliation score (continuous, centered around the mean), age (continuous, centered around the mean), gender presentation (male-presenting = -0.5, female-presenting = 0.5), and education (some = -0.5, none = 0.5), and the interaction between local affiliation, age, gender presentation, and education. Only speakers who had all three variable contexts in their interviews were included ($n=25$).

	Estimate	Std. error	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	-0.41	2.43	-0.17	0.87

Fixed effects					
Local affiliation	1.10	0.48	2.29	0.05	*
Age	0.09	0.12	0.79	0.45	
Gender	-2.07	4.85	-0.43	0.68	
Education	-1.74	4.85	-0.36	0.73	
Local affiliation:Age	-0.04	0.02	-1.49	0.17	
Local affiliation:Gender	0.72	0.97	0.75	0.47	
Local affiliation:Education	1.91	0.97	1.98	0.08	.
Age:Gender	0.01	0.24	0.05	0.96	
Age:Education	0.14	0.24	0.61	0.56	
Gender:Education	-2.43	9.71	-0.25	0.81	
Local affiliation:Age:Gender	-0.02	0.05	-0.31	0.76	
Local affiliation:Age:Education	-0.06	0.05	-1.30	0.23	
Local affiliation: Gender:Education	0.73	1.93	0.38	0.72	
Age:Gender:Education	0.11	0.47	0.23	0.83	
Local affiliation:Age:Gender:Education	0.06	0.10	0.63	0.55	

Visual inspection of Figure 6 reveals that there are several speakers with high local affiliation scores who do not use any of the nonstandard variants in their recording. One thing that they all have in common is that they have strong ties to the educational system, with four out of the five either being educators themselves or being married to educators. This suggests that education may influence the way speakers choose to express their local affiliation.

To determine if individual usage rates for the nonstandard variants correlate with each other, Pearson's product moment correlations were run for each variant pair (following Thorburn, 2014) in R (R Core Team, 2021), i.e., *was-them*, *was-come*, and *them-come*. These yield so-called *r*-values between +1 and -1, with the former indicating a positive correlation (i.e., rates of one variant increase as rates of the other variant increase) and the latter indicating a negative correlation (i.e., rates of one variant increase as rates of the other variant decrease). Since some individuals only had very few tokens per variable context, which could bias the results, speakers who contributed more than 5 tokens per context were included.

Table 5 shows the correlations between all three nonstandard variants for the whole community. Results indicate that there is only one significant correlation: the one between *was* and *them*, which is very strong ($r=.89, p<.01$). This is not surprising given that *was* and *them* are both agreement phenomena, which has been shown to facilitate correlations between variants in previous work (Oushiro & Guy 2015; Oushiro 2016).

Now that the community baseline has been established, how do the findings for particular social groups compare? Table 6 shows the pair-wise correlations for *was*, *them*, and *come* for speakers with high local affiliation. Similar to the community as a whole, only the correlation between *was* and *them* is statistically significant ($r=.84, p<.01$). The correlation is very strong ($r=.84$), but slightly weaker than the that for the whole community. The results for speakers with low local affiliation can be seen in Table 7. For this group, only the correlation between *was* and *come* could be calculated (which is not significant) because for the other variants pairings, only a handful of speakers fit the inclusion criteria, and none of them used nonstandard *was* or demonstrative *them* at all. This highlights the difficulty involved in conducting correlation analyses for morphosyntactic features, which tend to occur much less frequent than phonological variables.

Table 5: Correlations for the whole community (excluding speakers who had fewer than 5 tokens and speakers who did not have one or more of the relevant variable contexts)

<i>Was</i>		
$r=.89, p<.01$ (n=13)	<i>Them</i>	
$r=.32, p=.20$ (n=18)	$r=.30, p=.34$ (n=12)	<i>Come</i>

Table 6: Correlations for speakers with high local affiliation (i.e., local affiliation scores of 5 or higher, excluding speakers who had fewer than 5 tokens and speakers who did not have one or more of the relevant variable contexts)

<i>Was</i>		
$r=.84., p<.01$ (n=8)	<i>Them</i>	
$r=.08, p=.84$ (n=10)	$r=-.18, p=.70$ (n=7)	<i>Come</i>

Table 7: Correlations for speakers with low local affiliation (i.e., local affiliation scores of 4 or lower, excluding speakers who had fewer than 5 tokens and speakers who did not have one or more of the relevant variable contexts)

<i>Was</i>		
NA (n=5)	<i>Them</i>	
$r=-.11, p=.79$ (n=8)	NA (n=5)	<i>Come</i>

5. Discussion

The goal of this study was to determine if speakers with high local affiliation combined the nonstandard variants of these variables in systematic ways. Drawing on an ethnographically informed, discourse-based approach to measure local affiliation, results showed that local place ideologies in southern Aroostook County are strongly intertwined with ideologies of gender, with many participants mentioning that engaging in outdoor activities traditionally associated with men, such as hunting, is a crucial aspect of being from the County. Ethnicity is also implicated through frequent mentions of qualities like resilience and self-sufficiency, which are typically attributed to the white settlers who came to the area in the 19th century from Europe and other parts of the country. However, due to the sample being heavily biased towards white speakers, it is impossible to explore the role of this further without compromising the identity of the two Native American participants or expanding the sample.

The results of the correlation analysis add to the growing body of work showing that structural similarity promotes co-variation (in this case, shown by the two agreement phenomena, nonstandard *was* and *them*, being correlated), while social similarity between speakers does not,

or at least not necessarily (see Oushiro & Guy, 2015; Oushiro, 2016). For sociolinguistic theory, this implies that social factors may facilitate coherence in the repertoire of nonstandard morphosyntactic features, but not in usage. Given how little work has been done on the co-variation and co-occurrence of morphosyntactic features, future work should examine this trend more closely, drawing on a wider variety of features and communities.

While there is little evidence for systematic variation of usage rates, there is a clear pattern when it comes to speakers' repertoires, with speakers with high local affiliation, especially men, being more likely to use the nonstandard variants *was*, *them*, and *come* in their interviews. But individuals with ties to the education system do not conform to this pattern and usage rates vary widely. This suggests that the combination of nonstandard *was*, *them*, and *come* indexes high local affiliation for *some* speakers, but their absence does not imply the opposite. In other words, the combination of nonstandard variants has a different social meaning (namely, 'hard-working, no nonsense, with little regard for prescriptivism') compared to their absence (which has no clear social meaning), similar to the way that variants of the same variable can have non-complementary connotations. The most well-known example of this comes from Campbell-Kibler (2011): Looking at the realization of word-final (ing), she found that speakers rated the –ing pronunciation as more 'intelligent' and 'educated' as the -in realization, but –in was not rated the opposite way. Rather, it was seen as less formal than the –ing pronunciation, highlighting that both variants can index independent social meanings. Against this background, the findings of the present study suggest that the co-occurrence of linguistic features can be socially meaningful, regardless of whether rates of usage systematically co-vary or not.

However, these findings raise an important question: Why do women and speakers with ties to the education system not index their local affiliation by using the nonstandard variants *was*,

them, and *come*? Previous work has repeatedly shown that the correlation place attachment and nonstandard language use seems to be stronger for men than women (see Monka 2013; Monka, Quist & Skovse 2020; Beaman 2021), so the fact that only one female-presenting speaker exhibits this pattern is not surprising. However, the underlying reason for this recurring pattern is unclear. Eckert (1989:256) argues that women may be more “status-bound” than men, meaning they may see standard language use as one of the only ways to accumulate social capital. Given that nonstandard morphological features tend to be highly stigmatized, their tendency to avoid them may trump their desire to express their alignment with local values linguistically. But this type of sweeping generalization ignores the intersectional nature of gender, as well as the complexity of individual circumstances, as Eckert (2018:248) herself warns. To find a better answer to this question, it would be necessary to systematically explore the relationship between local affiliation and gender in different types of communities (e.g., urban and rural, big and small, ethnically diverse and mono-ethnic, etc.) to see if and where the pattern holds up.

When considering Aroostook County in isolation, the answer is more straightforward: As discussed earlier, local ideologies of place are highly gendered in nature, with many activities that are seen as typically local being traditionally masculine-coded, such as engaging in manual labor, hunting, and fishing. This pattern is reflected in the locally relevant persona of the *County Boy*, who embodies many of the values associated with life in the Country, such as being ‘resilient’ and ‘hard-working’. This character type enjoys the local life and does not bother with the pre-occupations of those living in the politically dominant South, including its institutions and their use of standard English. Importantly, this character type itself is highly gendered, and thus much more available for men than women. Moreover, it explicitly rejects the authority of institutions that are seen as antithetical to the traditional, rural lifestyle of Northern Maine, such as the

government or educational institutions. This makes it a less attractive model for those whose livelihood (at least in part) depends on the educational system, which is one of the largest employers in the communities where the fieldwork was conducted.¹² In a nutshell, the indexical meanings associated with the *County Boy* persona only appeal to a subset of the population with high local affiliation, explaining why the co-occurrence patterns identified in this study are not more widely embraced. These findings support the idea that socially recognized character types can play a key role in structuring local patterns of variation (Bigelow 2019; King 2021; Starr 2021; Esposito 2023).

It should be noted that there are numerous parallels in terms of my participants' concepts of local identity and those described in other studies of rural communities in the US (e.g., Roberts 2016) and Canada (e.g., Bigelow 2019; Schlegl 2019), especially the strong ideological link between the use of nonstandard linguistics forms and a more traditional way of life. Similar links between nonstandard variants and rurality have been described by Hall-Lew & Stephens (2012). Looking at metalinguistic commentary by speakers of English living at the border of Texas and Oklahoma, the authors find that when describing local ways of speaking, individuals often imagine a very specific type of rural persona (in their case, a manual laborer such as a cowboy or rancher) that uses a particular set of regional and non-regional features, all of them nonstandard. Interestingly, the participants in Hall-Lew & Stephens' (2012) study do mention demonstrative *them* and preterite forms in this context, indicating that these forms are socially meaningful outside of Aroostook County (Hall-Lew & Stephens 2012:264). However, they also mention a number of more explicitly Southern-coded forms such as the address term *y'all* and *fixin' to* (see Bailey, Wikle, Tillery & Sand 1993 for a more detailed analysis of the synchronic distribution of these features). These findings support the idea that there is a supra-local link between rurality and non-

standardness, but that the specific linguistic forms associated with rurality (be they in actual or imagined use) may vary depending on the locale. Future work should explore how these factors affect individuals' ideas about the relationship between language and place, and which linguistic and ideological features may characterize a pan-rural identity in the US and Canada.

6. Conclusion

This paper examined the influence of local affiliation on systematic variation of morphosyntactic features. Similarly to previous work, it finds limited evidence for socially motivated coherence in terms of usage rates. However, it uncovers that speakers with levels of local affiliation tend to draw on a similar inventory of (nonstandard) features in conversational speech. This result suggests that the extent to which different social groups draw on shared repertoires across speech situations and with different interlocutors (effectively combining traditional variationist methods with a third wave focus on stylistic practice) might be a fruitful avenue for future research. Moreover, the findings add empirical evidence to the growing body of work that shows that morphosyntactic features can be socially meaningful (see Moore 2024 for a more detailed discussion), opening the door for further explorations on what features or feature combinations are most likely to take on social meaning and how this social meaning is acquired and perceived.

On the methodological plane, this study has introduced an innovative, discourse-based metric for quantifying local affiliation. One of the core strengths of this metric, like any ethnographically informed score, is that it captures locally relevant social distinctions. While this means the metric are not directly transferable to other contexts, the methods used for developing the metric (specifically, the combination of thematic analysis and yes/no questions) can easily be adapted to other varieties and communities, making this paper an important step towards more

methodological coherence in the study of language and place (see Docherty, Travis & Gnevsheva 2024). In particular, the metric offers a model for researchers who wish to study the relationship between language and place in communities whose social and linguistic realities have not been described in much detail or which they enter as community outsiders because it allows researchers to capture participants' own understandings of what makes a place socially meaningful, helping to ensure our academic analyses are grounded in the experiences of those we as researchers aim to give a voice to.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to thank the participants in this study for sharing their stories with me. Moreover, I would like to express my gratitude to all those who supported me during data collection, especially the St. Pierre family, or who gave comments on earlier versions of this work, including Sali A. Tagliamonte, Derek Denis, Jessamyn Schertz, James Stanford, Naomi Nagy, Marisa Brook, as well as the audiences at NWAV 2022 and ICLaVE 2024. Finally, I would like to thank the many student assistants who have been involved in helping me transcribe the data, including Celine Chau, Diana Hamel, Milena Injac, Khadija Jagani, Sukhmani Khaira, Fatemeh Khavaninzadeh, Christopher Legerme, Yuen Ying Li, Shravani Patil, Jamie Stalcup, Preethi Vezhavendan, Shengqi Yang, Daphne van den Broeck, and Colin Veevers. All remaining errors are my own.

Funding statement

This research was approved by the University of Toronto Social Sciences, Humanities & Education Research Ethics Board, RIS Human Protocol Number 36161. All participants gave their express written consent to participate.

Endnotes

- 1 I am following Roberts' (2016) terminology here since her operationalization of the concept has been crucial to the discourse-based approach proposed here (see the data and methods section for details).
- 2 The term “nonstandard” is used here to refer to variants which would stand out as regionally or socially marked in Mainstream American English.
- 3 Note that existential constructions are not included here because almost all speakers engage in levelling in this context, not just those with high local affiliation.
- 4 In some varieties of English, *wasn't* is levelled to *weren't* in negative contexts, sometimes accompanied by *was* leveling in positive contexts (i.e., a mixed pattern). This second pattern is attested in various parts of England (Tagliamonte 1998; Britain 2002) as well as several historically isolated communities in the US (e.g., Schilling-Estes & Wolfram 1994; Schilling-Estes 2002), but not in Aroostook County.
- 5 Unless otherwise noted, all excerpts come from the County Corpus, a collection of sociolinguistic interviews from Northern Maine, and include the speaker's pseudonym, their gender presentation (assessed by the interviewer based on interview content), and their year of birth.
- 6 The shapefiles used to create this map were retrieved from U.S. Census Bureau (2018a); city coordinates are based on geohack.toolforge.org/geohack. I would like to thank [REDACTED] for help with creating this map.
- 7 The Webster-Ashburn Treaty is a peace agreement that effectively ended the Aroostook War, a land conflict between Maine and New Brunswick (Westaway McCue 2000).

- 8 Note that participants mentioned that there are also *County Girls*, especially when explicitly asked about this. However, whenever participants tried to describe them, they seemed to have a hard time doing so. This indicates that this persona (including its way of speaking) may not be as recognized – or as available – for women in this community.
- 9 To my knowledge, there is no work exploring place identity outside of the gender binary, highlighting the need for more intersectional work on place identity. More evidence for this comes from recent work on place and race, which shows that the field’s traditional focus on white speakers often paints those speakers’ language use as the default of what it means to ‘be’ from a certain place, relegating people of color to the sidelines, despite them being an integral part of these communities and often playing a key role in ongoing linguistic developments (see King 2021). This work shows that taking an intersectional approach to the study of language and place is crucial for understanding the unique, and sometimes conflicting perspectives of different groups inhabiting the same space (see also Ilbury’s (2022) ethnographic study of different perspectives on gentrification in East London).
- 10 Population numbers are based on estimates from the 2018 American Community Survey 5-Year Estimates. For more information, see U.S. Census Bureau (2018b, 2018c, 2018d, 2018e).
- 11 Following Hazen, Hamilton & Vacovsky (2011:84), instances where *them*, *those*, and *these* were used as demonstrative pronouns were not included since it is impossible to determine whether they serve as object pronouns or not.
- 12 It may also partly explain why preterite *come* is more wide-spread and potentially less crucial to the *County Boy* style than the other two features – it is less marked than the agreement violations, and thus not as strong a deviation from prescriptive norms.

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